

Diamagnetism in Evidence of I. P. of Niton.

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By using an apparatus almost similar to that used by Hertz and Kloppers in determining the ionisation potentials of rare gases, Holweck and Wertenstein (*Nature*, 1930, 126, 433) determined the I. P. of niton. Their method was to neutralise the negative space charge by accelerated positive ions from a subsidiary cathode. The quantity of niton used in their tube was of the order of 300 milli-curies giving an effective pressure of about 0.8 bar. At such low pressures, the number of ions produced by α -rays was negligibly small and thus it was believed that the gas behaved like any other permanent gas. They indicated I. P. for niton at 10.6 volts. Rasmussen (*Z. Physik*, 1930, 62, 7, 494) examined the spectral relations of the radium emanation in a discharge tube with admixtures of He, Ne, and A. With He and Ne mixtures, only the spark spectra appeared while with A-mixture, only the arc spectra were noticed. The lines of the arc spectrum were arranged in series and a number of strong terms and two resonance lines were noted. From this the series limit computed was $P_0 = 10.7$ volts. Evidently the process involved in this mode of excitation is due to a collision of the second kind which means that the reaction takes place between the radium emanation and the excited A atom raised to its metastable state (11.7 volts) or to its ionised state (15.5 volts); the more probable energy state to which niton is raised is to be determined by the close resonance between the energies of the exciting and the excited states. It is thus not altogether unlikely that I. P. of Niton is greater than that of xenon whose ionisation voltage lies at about 11.5 volts.

By a comparison of the ionisation values of a number of elements whose outermost electrons belong to N, O, and P-shells, it was shown (Biswas, *Phil. Mag.*, 1928, vii, 5, 1091) that the contiguous elements of same chemical family (iso-electronic elements) having outer N, O, and P-shells diminish in their ionisation values due to an increase of shells from N to O-shell but then suddenly increase again for the corresponding elements having outer P-shell. From the beginning of the P-shell with one outer electron in Au (79) to the addition of 5

electrons in Bi (83), *i. e.*, (to the addition of 3 electrons in 6₂ group after the completion of the subgroup 6₁ with two outer electrons) the rise in ionisation values of all the elements having outermost P-shell from the corresponding iso-electronic elements having outermost O-shell was unmistakably noticed.

TABLE I

N-shell		O-shell		P-shell.	
Cu	7.69	Ag	7.54	Au	9.25
Zn	9.35	Cd	8.95	Hg	10.39
Ga	5.97	In	5.76	Tl	6.68
Ge	7.85	Sn	7.38	Pb	7.93
As	9.40	Sb	8.0	Bi	8.0 ± 0.5
Kr	13.3	Xe	11.5	Nt	14.0 ± 0.5

Now the relation that has been found to hold so far till Bi, can surely be extended to the completion of the sub group 6₂ in Niton (86) and thus it is expected that the I. P. of Nt should be greater than that of Xenon. Ionisation values of the iso-electronic elements having successively the outer shells L, M, N, O, etc, fall off regularly and continuously fill the elements having outer O-shells are reached. Thus keeping aside the elements having outer P-shell the gradual diminution of the ionisation values with the increase of the number order of the shell is a common feature, which in no case has however been extended for any known I. P. of an element having its outer electron in P-shell (shells 1s to 5d completed with 78 electrons) and thus the extension of the relation that has subsisted among the rare gases from He till Xe, to Niton does not carry any weight.

It is proposed to argue on the evidence of the diamagnetic susceptibility that the elements having outer P-shell behave abnormally with respect to those having any other outer shell. L. Pauling (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, A, 114, 181) has obtained a formula for the diamagnetic susceptibility of a number of free atoms and ions.

$$\chi_a = -2.01 \times 10^{-6} \sum_k \frac{n_k^4}{(Z - SM_k)^2} \left[1 - \frac{\{3l_k(l_k + 1) - 1\}}{5n_k^2} \right]$$

in which χ_a = diamagnetic susceptibility for the atom, n , the total quantum number, $l = (k - 1)$, k being the old azimuthal quantum

number, Z =nuclear charge, S_{M_i} =screening constant for diamagnetism, \sum_i means that the summation extends over all electrons in the atom.

Specific susceptibilities per unit mass calculated by this equation are given below for the elements having outer N, O and P-shells.

TABLE II

 $-\chi \times 10^6$.

	N-shell	O-shell	P-shell
Cu	21 (18)	Ag	41 (30)
Zn	17 (15)	Cd	33 (18)
Ga	14 (24)	In	30 (11)
Ge	12 (12)	Sn	23 (35)?
As	10 (31)?	Sb	20 (82)
Kr	37	Xe	44
			Nt -41 (I.P.=10.6 volts)
			32(I.P.=14 ± 0.5 volts)

Clearly enough the specific susceptibilities for all the elements having outer O-shell increase in values from the corresponding elements having outer N-shell but these values decrease again for the elements of the same iso-electronic series having outer P-shell. It will thus be noticed that the relation with diamagnetism and ionisation voltages for the elements under different shells act exactly in opposite senses. It is thus believable that the specific susceptibility increases continuously for rare gases with the increase of the order of the shell till the outer O-shell is completed in xenon but diminishes again to a value even less than that of xenon with the increase of the next outer P-shell in niton.

Specific susceptibilities determined experimentally by Honda and Owen, in the metallic states of these elements are included within brackets in Table II, to show that the relation brought out by these values are quite in keeping with those calculated according to Pauling. Of these experimental values, those for In and As are doubtful due to impurities. Susceptibilities of Sb and Bi are already known to be abnormally high. Hence the values for Sb and Bi could not necessarily be fitted in the chart. These high values for Sb and Bi are possibly due to the fact that besides the effect of the electrons bound with the atom core (Pauling's χ values for Bi = 18×10^{-8}) the influence of the free conducting electrons and the influence of the

bindings of the crystal lattices play important parts to enhance in values.

Since diamagnetic susceptibilities primarily depend on the number of outer electron group, the mean susceptibility of the rare gas atoms-Kr, Xe, and Nt has been only approximately calculated for the electrons associated with (n, k) orbits orientated at random by evaluation of the quantum numbers of Pauling's equation with the assigned values of the group, while their effective charges have been only roughly eliminated by the values of the Ionisation Potentials corresponding to the removal of an electron of that group (Stoner, "Magnetism," p. 28). These values are included in Table II. It shows that χ for Nt is lower than that of xenon for both the values of I. P. of $10\cdot6$ and $14\cdot0 \pm 0\cdot5$ volts. For Kr, Xe, and Nt contributions due to the inner electron groups than the outer-most ones are not taken into account, hence these values are found much more reduced than Pauling's values for the same elements. Dia-magnetic susceptibility of Kr, Xe and Nt has also been calculated (Biswas, *Phys. Rev.* 1931, 38, 1784) according to Slater's method of charge distributions of the different electron shells in which the total quantum numbers of N, O, and P-shells have been substituted by their effective quantum numbers of 3·7, 4·0, and 4·5 respectively Slater, *Phys. Rev.*, 1930, 36, 57). This method gives a very low value of χ_a for Nt ($-46\cdot6 \times 10^{-6}$) which seems to support a lower χ value of niton.

Nielsen (*Nature.*, 1930, 18, 620) by a study of the spectroscopic data of Rasmussen (*loc.cit.*) has estimated the radial charge distributions of Nt according to Hartree's method of self consistent field. This offers another independent mode of checking χ for Nt which is proposed.

Incidentally it may be remarked here that the distinctive feature as exhibited by the elements having their outer-most electrons in P-shell as apart from the sequence that holds with the increase of the order of the shell till O-shell is completed, is seen to arise as due to the evaluation of the quantum numbers and the effective charges corresponding to their (n, k) group.